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INDEPENDENCE POLYNOMIALS $I_\alpha(G; x)$ AND MERRIFIELD-SIMMONS INDEXES

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ABSTRACT. In graph theory, independence polynomial $I_\alpha(G; x)$ is NP-hard (see [1] and [2]). In this paper, our ways are combinatorial counting methods. By means of the complementary of any stable set is a complete graph, conversely, the complementary of any complete graph is a stable set, the authors derive independence polynomial $I_\alpha(G; x)$, and present the explicit formulas of independence polynomials $I_\alpha(G; x)$ for a great deal of graphs, specially, independence polynomials of complete d -partite graph and $(n-3)$ -regular graph. Finally, Merrifield-Simmons indexes are given.

1. Introduction

In this paper, the authors will solve Independence polynomials $I_\alpha(G; x)$ and Merrifield-Simmons indexes.

Definition 1.1. In graph theory, stable set (or independent set) is the set of vertices in a graph , no two of which are adjacent. That is, it is a set S of vertices such that for every two vertices in S , there is no edge connecting the two.

Definition 1.2. Independent set polynomials $I(G; x)$ are defined as

$$I(G; x) = \sum_{k=1}^n b_k(G)x^k = \sum_{I \subset v(G)} \prod_{v \in I} x,$$

where let $b_k(G)$ be exactly k -independent sets of G .

Complexity: It is easy to see that $I(G; x)$ is NP-hard to compute. (see [1])

Definition 1.3. If s_k denotes the number of stable sets of cardinality k in graph G , and $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum stable set, then

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} s_k x^k$$

is called independence polynomial of G .

(Also see [2])

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Definition 1.4. For Merrifield-Simmons index of the graph, denoted by $i(G)$, Merrifield-Simmons proposed, it is defined as the number of all independent sets of the graph, including the empty set.

$S(G)$ denotes the number of all stable sets in G , namely,

$$S(G) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} s_k.$$

Remark:(reviewing the size of maximum independent set) Because it is NP-hard that $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum stable set (the size of maximum independent set), so far there exists not the explicit formula, a number of mathematicians have studied that $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum stable set(the size of maximum independent set). Enumeration of $S(G)$ is more difficult than $\alpha(G)$.

2. Basic Lemmas

In the section, the authors will state some basic Lemmas used in the article.

Lemma 2.1. *If s_k denotes the number of stable sets of cardinality k in graph G , and c_k denotes the number of complete subgraphs of order k in \bar{G} , then $s_k = c_k$.*

Proof. Our idea is that two sets have the same cardinal number if there exists a 1-1 correspondence between them. Because the complementary of any stable set is a complete graph, conversely, the complementary of any complete graph is a stable set, then there exists a 1-1 correspondence between stable sets of cardinality k in G and complete subgraphs of order k in \bar{G} , so $s_k = c_k$. \square

Lemma 2.2. *If $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum stable set in G , then $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum complete graph in \bar{G} .*

Proof. Omitted. \square

3. Main results

In the section, the authors will discuss independence polynomials $I_\alpha(G; x)$ of graphs.

Theorem 3.1. *If c_k denotes the number of complete subgraphs of order k in \bar{G} , then independence polynomials $I_\alpha(G; x)$ of graphs are as follows:*

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k x^k,$$

where $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum complete graph in \bar{G} .

Proof. By definition 1.3 , Lemma 2.1 and Lemma 2.2, then

$$\begin{aligned} I_\alpha(G; x) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} s_k x^k \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k x^k, \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum complete graph in \bar{G} . \square

Theorem 3.2. *If G is a graph with n vertices, the degree sequence of G is d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n , \bar{G} is no K_3 subgraph, then*

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + \left[\binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} \right] x^2.$$

Proof. Because \bar{G} is no K_3 subgraph, a maximum complete graph in \bar{G} is K_2 , then $\alpha(G) = 2$.

c_k = the number of complete subgraphs of order k in \bar{G} ,

$c_1 = n$

the number of edges of $G = \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2}$,

the number of edges of $\bar{G} = \binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2}$,

then $c_2 = \binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2}$.

Finally, according to Theorem 3.1, the result is derived as follows:

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + \left[\binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} \right] x^2.$$

\square

Theorem 3.3. *If G is a complete d -partite graph $K_{n, n, \dots, n}$, the number of n is d , then*

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = d(1 + x)^n - d.$$

Proof. Suppose that G is a complete d -partite graph $K_{n, n, \dots, n}$, the number of n is d , then $\bar{G} = K_n \cup K_n \cup \dots \cup K_n$, and the number of K_n is d .

c_1 is the number of complete subgraphs of order 1 in \bar{G} , $c_1 = d \binom{n}{1}$;

c_2 is the number of complete subgraphs of order 2 in \bar{G} , $c_2 = d \binom{n}{2}$;

.....

c_k is the number of complete subgraphs of order k in \bar{G} , $c_k = d \binom{n}{k}$;

.....

c_n is the number of complete subgraphs of order n in \bar{G} , $c_n = d \binom{n}{n}$;

$\alpha(G) = n$

Finally, according to Theorem 3.1, then

$$\begin{aligned} I_\alpha(G; x) &= d \binom{n}{1} x + d \binom{n}{2} x^2 + \dots + d \binom{n}{k} x^k + \dots + d \binom{n}{n} x^n \\ &= d \left[1 + \binom{n}{1} x + \binom{n}{2} x^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{k} x^k + \dots + \binom{n}{n} x^n \right] - d \\ &= d(1 + x)^n - d. \end{aligned}$$

\square

Theorem 3.4. *If $G = K_{1, n-1}$ is a star graph with n vertices, then*

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = (x - 1) + (1 + x)^{n-1}.$$

Proof. Because of $G = K_{1,n-1}$, $\bar{G} = K_1 \cup K_{n-1}$ then $c_1 = n; c_2 = \binom{n-1}{2}; \dots; c_k = \binom{n-1}{k}; \dots; c_{n-1} = \binom{n-1}{n-1}$. $\alpha(G) = n - 1$. By Theorem 3.1 then

$$\begin{aligned} I_\alpha(G; x) &= nx + \binom{n-1}{2}x^2 + \dots + \binom{n-1}{k}x^k + \dots + \binom{n-1}{n-1}x^{n-1} \\ &= (x-1) + 1 + \binom{n-1}{1}x + \binom{n-1}{2}x^2 + \dots + \binom{n-1}{k}x^k + \dots + \binom{n-1}{n-1}x^{n-1} \\ I_\alpha(G; x) &= (x-1) + (1+x)^{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.5. *If G is a $(n-2)$ -regular graph with n (even $2m$) vertices, then independence polynomial of G is as follows:*

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + \frac{n}{2}x^2.$$

Proof. Let G be a $(n-2)$ -regular graph with n (even $2m$), then \bar{G} is a 1-regular graph, namely, $\bar{G} = K_2 \cup K_2 \cup \dots \cup K_2$, and the number of K_2 is m . Because \bar{G} is no K_3 subgraph, according to Theorem 3.2,

$$\begin{aligned} I_\alpha(G; x) &= nx + \left[\binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} \right] x^2, \\ d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n &= n(n-2) \\ I_\alpha(G; x) &= nx + \frac{n}{2}x^2. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.6. *If G is a $n-3$ -regular graph with n vertices, $n \geq 6$, and $\bar{G} \cong C_n$, then independence polynomial of G is as follows:*

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + nx^2.$$

Proof. Let G be a $n-3$ -regular graph with n vertices, $n \geq 6$ and $\bar{G} \cong C_n$, because \bar{G} is a 2-regular graph, the graph would be able to join the disjoint cycles, thus assume that C_n , say. Because \bar{G} is no K_3 subgraph, according to Theorem 3.2,

$$\begin{aligned} I_\alpha(G; x) &= nx + \left[\binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} \right] x^2, \\ d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n &= n(n-3) \\ I_\alpha(G; x) &= nx + nx^2. \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 3.7. *If G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph with n vertices, and*

$$\bar{G} = C_{n_1} \cup C_{n_2} \cup \dots \cup C_{n_q},$$

$n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_q = n$, $C_{n_i} \cap C_{n_j} = \phi$ for any i and j , $i \neq j$, $3 \leq n_j \leq n$, $1 \leq j \leq q$, $q \geq 1$, $n \geq 6$, the number of $n_j = 3$ is l , then independence polynomial of G is given as follows:

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + nx^2 + lx^3.$$

Proof. c_k = the number of complete subgraphs of order k in \bar{G} ,
 $\bar{G} = C_{n_1} \cup C_{n_2} \cup \dots \cup C_{n_q}$, $n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_q = n$, $C_{n_i} \cap C_{n_j} = \phi$ for any i and j , $i \neq j$, $3 \leq n_j \leq n$, $1 \leq j \leq q$, $q \geq 1$, $n \geq 6$, the number of $n_j = 3$ is l ,
 so $c_1 = n; c_2 = n; c_3 = l$; $\alpha(G) = 3$. According to Theorem 3.1,

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k x^k$$

$$= nx + nx^2 + lx^3.$$

□

Theorem 3.8. *If T is a tree with n vertices, then*

$$I_\alpha(\bar{T}; x) = nx + (n - 1)x^2.$$

Proof. Suppose that T is a tree with n vertices, the degree sequence of T is d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n , then T is no K_3 subgraph, and the degree sequence of \bar{T} is $n - 1 - d_1, n - 1 - d_2, \dots, n - 1 - d_n$. According to Theorem 3.2,

$$I_\alpha(\bar{T}; x) = nx + \left[\binom{n}{2} - \frac{(n - 1 - d_1) + (n - 1 - d_2) + \dots + (n - 1 - d_n)}{2} \right] x^2$$

$$= nx + \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} x^2$$

$$d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n = 2\varepsilon = 2(n - 1)$$

$$I_\alpha(\bar{T}; x) = nx + (n - 1)x^2.$$

□

4. Merrifield-Simmons index

In the setion, the authors will discuss Merrifield-Simmons indexes of graphs.

Theorem 4.1. *If $S(G)$ denotes the number of all stable sets of a graph in G , namely,*

$$S(G) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} s_k,$$

then

$$S(G) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k,$$

where $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum complete graph in \bar{G} .

Proof. By Lemma 2.1, $s_k = c_k$, By Lemma 2.2, $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum stable set in G , $\alpha(G)$ is the size of a maximum complete graph in \bar{G} , so

$$S(G) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} s_k$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k.$$

□

Theorem 4.2. *If $S(G)$ denotes the number of all stable sets of a graph in G , then*

$$S(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1).$$

Proof.

$$S(G) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k.$$

By Theorem 3.1,

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k x^k.$$

Let $x = 1$. Then

$$S(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1).$$

□

Theorem 4.3. *If G is any graph, then the relation between independences polynomial and Merrifield-Simmons index is as follows:*

$$i(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1) + 1.$$

Proof.

$$i(G) = S(G) + 1 = I_\alpha(G; 1) + 1.$$

□

Theorem 4.4. *Suppose that G is a complete d -partite graph $K_{n,n,\dots,n}$, the number of n is d , then*

$$i(G) = d2^n - d + 1.$$

Proof. Method 1 Because of

$$\begin{aligned} S(G) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k = \sum_{k=1}^n d \binom{n}{k} \\ &= d \sum_{k=1}^n \binom{n}{k} \\ &= d \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} - d \\ &= d2^n - d, \end{aligned}$$

then

$$i(G) = S(G) + 1 = d2^n - d + 1.$$

Method 2

By Theorem 3.3,

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = d(1+x)^n - d.$$

By Theorem 4.3,

$$i(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1) + 1 = d2^n - d + 1.$$

□

Theorem 4.5. *If $G = K_{1, n-1}$ is a star graph with n vertices, then*

$$i(G) = 2^{n-1} + 1.$$

Proof. Method 1 For

$$\begin{aligned} S(G) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha(G)} c_k \\ &= n + \binom{n-1}{2} + \dots + \binom{n-1}{k} + \dots + \binom{n-1}{n-1} \\ &= 1 + \binom{n-1}{1} + \binom{n-1}{2} + \dots + \binom{n-1}{k} + \dots + \binom{n-1}{n-1} \\ &= 2^{n-1}, \end{aligned}$$

then

$$i(G) = S(G) + 1 = 2^{n-1} + 1.$$

Method 2

By Theorem 3.4,

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = (x-1) + (1+x)^{n-1}.$$

By Theorem 4.3,

$$i(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1) + 1 = 2^{n-1} + 1. \quad \square$$

Theorem 4.6. *If G is a $(n-2)$ -regular graph with n (even $2m$) vertices, then*

$$i(G) = \frac{3n}{2} + 1.$$

Proof. Omitted. □

Theorem 4.7. *If G is a $n-3$ -regular graph with n vertices, $n \geq 6$, and $\bar{G} \cong C_n$, then*

$$i(G) = 2n + 1.$$

Proof. Omitted. □

Corollary 4.8. *If G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph with n vertices, and*

$$\bar{G} = C_{n_1} \cup C_{n_2} \cup \dots \cup C_{n_q},$$

$n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_q = n$, $C_{n_i} \cap C_{n_j} = \phi$ for any i and j , $i \neq j$, $3 \leq n_j \leq n$, $1 \leq j \leq q$, $q \geq 1$, $n \geq 6$, the number of $n_j = 3$ is l , then

$$i(G) = 2n + l + 1.$$

Proof. By Corollary 3.7,

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + nx^2 + lx^3.$$

By Theorem 4.3,

$$i(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1) + 1 = n + n + l + 1 = 2n + l + 1. \quad \square$$

Theorem 4.9. *If T is a tree with n vertices, then*

$$i(\bar{T}) = 2n.$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.8,

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + (n - 1)x^2.$$

By Theorem 4.3,

$$i(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1) + 1 = n + (n - 1) + 1 = 2n - 1 + 1 = 2n.$$

□

Theorem 4.10. *If G is a graph with n vertices, the degree sequence of G is d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n , \bar{G} is no K_3 subgraph, then*

$$i(G) = n + \binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} + 1.$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.2,

$$I_\alpha(G; x) = nx + \left[\binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} \right] x^2.$$

By Theorem 4.3,

$$i(G) = I_\alpha(G; 1) + 1 = n + \binom{n}{2} - \frac{d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_n}{2} + 1.$$

□

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